

Clinico-Pathological Study of Acute Kidney Injury (AKI) in Term and Preterm New-Borns Admitted to a Tertiary Care Center**Rakesh Kumar Routray¹, Benoj Kr Maji², Rokaiyya Anis³, Nandan Rudra⁴, Pradyut Kumar Mandal⁵, Saroj Kumar Satapathy⁶**¹Assistant Professor, Department of Nephrology, S.C.B. Medical College, Manglabag, Cuttack 753007, Odisha, India²Assistant Professor, Department of Paediatrics, Gouri Devi Institute of Medical Science and Hospital, Rajbandh 713212, West Bengal, India^{3,4}Assistant Professor, Department of Paediatrics, Santiniketan Medical College & Hospital, Vill-Gobindapur, P.O- Muluk, Bolpur 731204, West Bengal, India⁵Professor, Department of Paediatrics, Santiniketan Medical College & Hospital, Vill- Gobindapur, P.O- Muluk, Bolpur 731204, West Bengal, India⁶Ex-Professor and Head, Department of Paediatrics, S.C.B. Medical College, Manglabag, Cuttack 753007, Odisha, India

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:**Background:** Acute kidney injury (AKI), frequently involving patients admitted to the neonatal intensive care unit (NICU), is associated with poor outcomes and affects 18–70% of critically ill neonates. The present study was undertaken in the Department of Pediatrics, SCB Medical College & SVPPGIP, Cuttack to evaluate the occurrence of neonatal AKI and delineate the risk factors associated with it and short-term outcomes of AKI in neonates admitted in this hospital, which is a tertiary care center.**Methodology:** The study population included term and preterm sick neonates admitted to the NBU. The study was carried during the period December-2012 to September-2014. Newborns with no AKI with no other confounding factors were picked up to serve as control. Renal function parameters such as blood urea, serum creatinine, serum electrolytes, urinary sodium and creatinine were monitored on admission to NBU. Those babies having abnormal renal function had their laboratory parameters monitored every alternate day till discharge. Pediatric Urobag was used aseptically to collect urine over 24hrs. The Ultrasonographic examination performed in the study was done using gray scale real time machine (Nebula 402) employing a 5 to 7.5 MHZ transducer. All the details of the case were recorded in the proforma and analysed. The Statistical Products and Services Solutions (SPSS) software version 17.0 was used to analyze the data and created reports and graphs. Help of socialstatistics.com from Internet was taken to analyse the data.**Results:** In this prospective study 2100 newborns admitted to SNCU were screened for AKI based on urine output (<1ml/kg/hr), blood urea nitrogen and serum creatinine. Approx. 118 neonates (5.6%) of the hospitalised were affected by AKI. So the incidence of AKI is 5.6%. About 55.08% of the affected were Preterms. Males were affected more than females. Neonates weighing <2500 gm were around 72% which indicates that prematurity and low birth weight are risk factors for AKI. The most common causes of AKI were sepsis (72%), followed by birth asphyxia (28%), PDA (4.23%), RDS (3.38%), and PUV (2.5%). Both sepsis and birth asphyxia combined together contributed towards maximum number of AKI.**Conclusion:** The present study and observations clearly revealed that AKI is an increasingly recognised entity among critically ill neonates. In this study sepsis, birth asphyxia, RDS, PDA, PUV were common predisposing factors for AKI. Low birth weight and prematurity are important risk factors for the development of AKI. The most common causes of neonatal death in AKI in the present study was consistent with the most common causes of neonatal death including infections, prematurity and asphyxia. Higher mortality rate was associated with oliguric AKI states.**Keywords:** Acute kidney injury (AKI), term, preterm, newborn, outcomes.This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.**Introduction**

Compromised kidney function in the perinatal period has been increasingly recognised during

recent years and acute kidney injury is a frequent clinical situation in neonatal care units. (Burghard

R, Leititis JU, Brandies M et al 1987) [1]. Their review mainly focuses on early diagnosis of disturbed neonatal kidney function and prophylactic therapeutically aspects which may be of particular benefit for critically ill newborns at high risk for developing acute kidney injury.

According to NF Ahmed Azat, et al [2] acute kidney injury is defined as an acute deterioration in ability of the kidneys to maintain homeostasis of body fluids, electrolytes and is associated with acute decrease in the rate of glomerular filtration (GFR) that leads to retention of waste and toxic metabolic end products.

Acute kidney injury (AKI), frequently involving patients admitted to the neonatal intensive care unit (NICU), is associated with poor outcomes and affects 18–70% of critically ill neonates. Although the real incidence of AKI in neonates is uncertain, with wide and various ranges, due to several definitions and diagnostic methods, more immature and ill neonates are characterized by the highest risk of AKI [3]. Jetton JG, et al 2012 [4] stated that acute kidney injury (AKI) is associated with increased risk of morbidity and mortality in critically ill newborns. The incidence of AKI in neonatal ICU ranges from 8-20%. Despite better understanding of the pathophysiology and improved therapy, the mortality in neonates with AKI is very high. Although data from neonatal AKI research has been sparse until recently, previous epidemiology studies have suggested that AKI in neonates is common and those with AKI are at risk for death and long term chronic kidney disease [5]. Considering the high incidence rate of AKI (8-24%) in hospitalised newborns and the high mortality rate of this disease (20-50%) it is one of the most important disease among hospitalised patients in tertiary care center [6].

In this prospective study the aim was to catch the incidence of AKI in all newborns irrespective of their initial diagnosis. By this the picture of AKI from among a large pool of newborns was clear. The aim was to find out factors which are attributable to AKI in newborns. Factors like prematurity, very low birth weight, newborns with congenital heart disease, perinatal depression, and sepsis are studied in detail in relation to development of AKI. The clinical presentations of newborns developing AKI was studied in details and in this study the correlation of clinical features with AKI was to be delineated [7]. This prospective study was also emphasized the pathological and biochemical abnormality in AKI affected newborns. Our ability to improve outcomes for these patients depends on heightened awareness of this issue so that early steps can be taken to improve the outcome.

Materials & Methods

The hospital based prospective observational study was conducted at the Newborn unit (NBU) in the Department of Pediatrics SCB Medical College & SVPPGIP, Cuttack, which is a tertiary referral and teaching hospital. It is also the main in-patient hospital and admits all sick neonates, those born outside and also handles transfer from other hospital. The study population included term and preterm sick neonates admitted to the NBU. The study was carried during the period December-2012 to September-2014. Individual participants were in the study from birth or admission to discharge from our hospital. Data analysis, presentation to the department was completed within the study period.

Inclusion Criteria:

All newborns admitted to SNCU were screened for AKI and included in the study.

Criteria for AKI in the study in defined as:

- Oliguria i.e. urine output <1ml/Kg/hr.
- Blood urea nitrogen (BUN) > 20 mg/dl on two separate occasions at least 24 hrs apart.
- Serum creatinine levels > 1.5 mg/dl.

After consent by the parent or care giver these criteria were implemented and if 2 of the 3 criteria were present the case was picked up for study.

Exclusion Criteria:

- Those newborns not satisfying the criteria of AKI were excluded from the study.
- Refusal to consent by parents or care giver.

Investigations

New-born with no AKI with no other confounding factors were picked up to serve as control. Renal function parameters such as blood urea, serum creatinine, serum electrolytes, urinary sodium and creatinine were monitored on admission to NBU. Those babies having abnormal renal function had their laboratory parameters monitored every alternate day till discharge. Serum creatinine was determined by Photometric determination of creatinine based Jaffe kinetic method with deproteinisation. Serum urea determination was done by photometric determination according to urease GLDH method. Serum and urinary electrolytes were estimated by using chloride kit (Thiocyanate method), Elyte 2 Kit (Naek colorimeter). Pediatric Urobag was used aseptically to collect urine over 24hrs. The ultrasonographic examination performed in the study was done using gray scale real time machine (Nebula 402) employing a 5 to 7.5 MHZ transducer. All the ultrasonography was done in the Department of Radiodiagnosis. All the investigations were done in the Department of Biochemistry and Department of

Pathology SCB Medical College and SVPPGIP, Cuttack. All the details of the case were recorded in the proforma and analysed. The Statistical Products and Services solutions (SPSS) software version 17.0 was used to analyze the data and created reports and graphs. Help of socialstatistics.com from Internet was taken to analyse the data.

Sampling Technique:

All sick newborns (term and preterm) who satisfied the inclusion criteria were enrolled. The parents or caregivers of the neonates that met the inclusion criteria were requested to participate in the study. Written informed consent was obtained after clear explanation of the purpose of the study, expected benefits and potential harms. Newborns who died within 3 days of admission were excluded from the study. The blood sample was collected on day 3 of life or on admission for investigation and analysis.

Sepsis Screening:

1. CRP was measured by Turbidimetric immunoassay. Reference values of CRP in normal population are <0.6 mg/dl.
2. Micro ESR: Micro ESR is obtained by collecting capillary blood in a standard. Preheparinized Microhematocrit glass tube (75 mm length, internal diameter 1.1mm, outer diameter 1.5mm), placing it vertically and reading the fall in red cell column after hour. The normal value (mm 1st hr) is equal to postnatal days of life plus 2mm. Peak value is 15mm at the end of 1st hour during neonatal period.
3. Total Leucocyte Count: Using WBC Pipette, WBC diluting fluid, total leucocyte count was calculated in Neubauer's chamber.
4. Immature to total neutrophil ratio: A band cell was defined as a neutrophil in which the nucleus was indented by more than one half, but

in which the isthmus between the lobe was wide enough to have two distinct margins with nuclear material between the lobes. Band to total neutrophil ratio of >0.2 was considered significant.

5. Blood Culture: Blood was collected after cleaning the puncture site thoroughly with alcohol, followed by povidone - iodine and followed again by alcohol. Povidone - iodine was applied in a concentric circles moving outward from centre. The skin was allowed to dry for at least minute before the sample was collected. With a 2ml disposable syringe and 22 gauge needles 1ml of blood was inoculated in 5ml of Glucose Citrate broth in one ounce screw capped bottle. This was incubated at 37°C for 18 to 48 hours. If the medium showed any turbidity after incubation, it was sub-cultured on blood agar and Mac Conkey's agar plate for 48 hours from a single isolated colony, smears were prepared and examined by Gram's Stain. The organism was identified and antibiotic sensitivity was tested by using filter paper disc diffusion technique. Blood Urea Nitrogen (BUN) was determined using diacetyl monoxime method. Serum creatinine estimation was determined by alkaline picrate.

Results

The following observations were made from the present study conducted in SNCU and Dept of pediatrics SCB Medical College and SVPPGIP, Cuttack. From 2100 patients received in SNCU, 118 patients were diagnosed as acute kidney injury (AKI) according to the criteria fixed at the beginning of the study. The incidence is around 5.6%. These 118 cases were studied for the clinical presentation, distribution of AKI with associated risk factors and outcomes.

Table 1: Newborn received in SNCU and affected with AKI

No. of Newborns received	2100
Newborns affected with AKI	118
Incidence	5.6%

Table 1 shows the incidence of AKI in our study is 5.6%.

Table 2: Sex, body weight and gestational age distribution of affected AKI

Sex	Number	Percentage
Male	70	59.32
Female	48	40.67
Birth weight		
1000-1499 gms	32	27.11
1500-2499 gms	53	44.91
2500 gms	33	27.96
Gestational age		
Term	53	44.91
Preterm	65	55.08
Total	118	100%

Table 2 shows Male 70 cases (59.32%) and Female 48 cases (40.67%). Table 2 shows newborns <1500 gms constitute 27.11%. Newborns 1500-2499 Gms constitute 44.91% and 2500 Gms constitute 27.96%. It shows preterm constitute 55.08% of the total AKI cases.

Table 3: No. of control and AKI newborn in both study groups according to sex and gestational age

Sex	AKI	Percentage	Non AKI	Percentage
Male	70	59.32	68	57.62
Female	48	40.67	50	42.37
Gestational Age				
Term	53	44.91	54	45.76
Preterm	65	55.08	64	54.23

Table 3 shows comparison of new-borns included in AKI group and control group.

Table 4: Distribution according to day of presentation

Day of Presentation	Number	Percentage
0 to 3	52	44.06
4 to 7	62	52.51
8 to 14	04	3.38
Total	118	100%

Table 4 shows that 52 (44%) cases present during 1st 3days, 62(52.51%) present between 4-7 days and 4(3.38%) cases present between 8-14 days.

Table 5: Mean days of presentation of AKI

Day of Presentation	Frequency	Mean (Day)
0-3	52	-
4-7	62	3.95 days
8-14	04	-

Table 5 shows most of the AKI neonates present at initial presentation and mean day of presentation is 3.95 days.

Table 6: Etiological distribution of AKI

Etiology	Number	Percentage
Sepsis	72	61.01
Birth Asphyxia	34	28.81
PDA	05	4.23
RDS	04	3.38
PUV	03	2.54
Total	118	100 %

Table 6 shows Sepsis 72 cases (61.01%), Birth Asphyxia 34 cases (28.81%), PDA 5 cases (4.23%), RDS 4 cases (3.38%), PUV 3 cases (2.54%) respectively.

Table 7: Distribution according to pre/post-renal and oliguria AKI

Type of AKI	No.	Percentage
Pre-renal	81	68.64
Renal	34	28.81
Post-renal	03	2.54
According to oliguric and non-oliguric		
Oliguric	71	60.16
Non-oliguric	47	39.83

Table 7 shows Pre-renal AKI in 68.64% of cases followed by Renal in 28.81% and Post-renal in 2.54% cases. It also shows 71 cases to be oliguric (60.16%) and 47 non-oliguric cases (39.83%).

Table 8: Outcome of AKI

Outcome	Total	Percentage
Death	42	36
Survival	76	64
Total	118	100%

Table 8 shows death in 42 cases (36%) and survival in 76 cases (64%) of the 118 cases affected with AKI.

Table 9: Comparison of neonates with oliguric and non-oliguric AKI

Characteristics	Oliguric	Non-oliguric	P-Value
No. of Patients	71	47	0.85
Mean Gestational age	35.2	35.45	0.38
Mean Wt (gm)	1981	2085	0.49
Mean day of presentation	3.95	4.21	0.3
Mortality (No.)	26	16	0.77

Table 9 shows prematurity and low birth weight were independent risk factor for AKI. Mortality was high in oliguric AKI in comparison to non-oliguric AKI.

Table 10: Ultrasonography findings in newborns affected with AKI

No. of Cases	Finding	Percentage
106	Normal	89.83
09	Medical Renal Disease	7.62
03	Congenital anomaly	2.54
Total	118	100 %

Table 10 shows normal sonographic finding in 89% of the AKI affected new borns.

Discussion

The study was a hospital based study. The prospective study was conducted from Dec 2012-Oct 2014 in SNCU SCB Medical College and SVPPGIP, Cuttack. Total number of babies admitted to SNCU was 2100. Out of which 118 babies fitted to the criteria of AKI which was decided before the start of the study.

Table 1 Shows the incidence of AKI in sick newborns in our set up was 5.6%. Kribben A et al, 1999 in their study found AKI is a common renal disease affecting upto 5% of all hospitalised patients [8]. Subramanian S et al, 2008 [9] also stated the incidence of AKI to be 4-6% of total hospitalised newborns. Gharebbagi MM et al, 2007 [10] found the incidence to be 2.83% in their study. Hossein et al, 2014 [11] found the incidence to be 1.54%. Al – Idressy HM et al, 1991 [12] stated the incidence of neonatal AKI was 3.6% in their study. Our study noted an incidence of 5.6% and hence lying within the range of most of the studies done.

Table 2 shows that of 118 AKI newborns 70(59.32%) were male and 48(40.67%) were female. Gendes JS and Polin RA et al 1987 [13] reported that male newborn have more chance of developing AKI compared to females. Airede et al, 1997 [14] study showed that incidence and outcome of AKI also found males affected more than females. Mortazavi F et al, 2009 [10] stated a more number of male neonates affected with AKI. Gharebbagi et al, 2007 [15] stated males having a higher incidence of AKI. Hence our study is consistent with most of the studies. However Hossein et al, 2014 [11] found in their study that 87.8% of the study were female and only 12.2% were male.

Table 2 shows newborns <2500gm constitute 72%. Low birth weight is an important risk factor for

development of AKI. Takker VP et al 1997 [16] reported low birth weight to be an important risk factor for AKI. Singh M et al, 1994 [17] reported low birth weight constitute an important risk factor for development of acute renal failure. In Mathur et al [18] the birth weight of < 2500 gram was higher than in healthy neonates. The mean birth weight in our study is 1981gm which is consistent with other studies. However in Hossien et al study [11] only 38.3% of newborns have birth weight of <2500 gram.

Table 2 shows 55.08% of newborns were preterm. In Agras Pl et al, 2004 [19] term newborn constituted around 69%. In Gharebaghi MM et al study [15] most of involved patients were term (70.6%). However Takker VP et al, 1997 [16] found prematurity as an important risk factor.

Al Idressy HM et al, 1991 [12] found half of the patients were born at less than 32 weeks gestation. And less than 1500 gm. Takker VP et al 1997 [16] & Singh M, et al 1994 [17] reported prematurity are risk factors for AKI in newborn from Indian study. Our study also states the number of Preterms to be high but found no statistical significance. Table 3 shows the number of control cases in our study. The number of control cases 118 in which 68 were male and 50 were female. Pre-terms in the control group were 64 and term 54. So in our study the control group was equally matched with the study group.

Table 4 we find that the majority i.e. 53% cases presented between 0-7 days of life. Table 5 mean day of presentation is 3.95 days. AKI was present at the onset in most of the patients in the present study. Mathur NB, et al, 2007 [18] showed AKI was present at the onset in 60% of patients. Such a high percentage reinforces the fact that the neonatal kidney is very fragile and that the latent period for the onset of renal failure may be very short. In Mathur et al study [18] the majority of presentation of AKI was between 0-7 days of life. In contrast

Bourquia A et al, 1993 [20] reported the median age of onset of symptomatic events to be 7 days.

Table 6 depicts the most common etiology in our study is sepsis 72 cases (61.01%) followed by birth asphyxia 34 cases (28.81%), PDA 5 cases (4.23%), RDS 4 cases (2.54%). Our study is consistent with the above studies. Mathur NB et al [18] also attributed sepsis as one of the most important cause of AKI. However Agras PL et al 2004 [19] stated Birth asphyxia as the most common cause that contributed to AKI.

Asphyxia contributed to around 40% in their study. Aierede A, et al, 1997 [14] in their study of AKI in newborn found perinatal asphyxia, sepsis, obstructive uropathy and miscellaneous contribute 53.4%, 32.6%, 9.3% and 4.7% cases respectively. Mohd Abu-Haweleh et al, 1998 [21] showed neonatal asphyxia was the most common cause of AKI in newborns accounting for 42 accounted for 15.7% cases followed by drugs (aminoglycosides and vancomycin). Al-Idresly HM, et al, 1991 [12] showed AKI developed in 3.6% of babies and the most frequent causes were hypotension (86%), respiratory distress syndrome (41%), sepsis (32%) and asphyxia (27%). Gouyon JB, Guignard JP et al, 2000 [22] showed the leading causes of AKI in newborns were perinatal anoxia-ischemia and sepsis.

In many studies, % of renal failure and was associated with highest mortality rate 70%. Septicemia accounted for 15.7% cases followed by drugs (aminoglycosides and vancomycin). Al-Idresly HM, et al, 1991 [12] showed AKI developed in 3.6% of babies and the most frequent causes were hypotension (86%), respiratory distress syndrome (41%), sepsis(32%) and asphyxia (27%). Gouyon JB, Guignard JP et al, 2000 [22] showed the leading causes of AKI in newborns were perinatal anoxia-ischemia and sepsis.

In many studies, perinatal asphyxia has been considered as the most prevalent cause of AKI higher than sepsis which was not consistent with the present observation. This may be due to more precise documentation of immediate, prenatal, delivery room and postnatal condition of the fetus and newborn in other studies ,which has revealed perinatal asphyxia and we have not taken the data of all inborn rather most of them were outborns received in our SNCU. However in all above studies sepsis and birth asphyxia in combination is probably the most common etiology contributing to AKI in newborns which is consistent with our study.

Table 7 shows pre-renal AKI in our study was 68.64% followed by renal 28.81% and post-renal 2.54% of the cases. Our study is consistent with the study of Hossein Mamtaz [11] who found 71% pre-renal AKI cases in their study. However Mortazavi

F et al [10] and Al Idressy HM [12] found more number of intrinsic renal cases in their study.

Table 7, 9 shows most of the AKI were oliguric 60.16% and non-oliguric 39.83%. Agras PL et al, 2004 [19] stated 53% of patients were oliguric and 47% of the cases were nonoliguric AKI. Hossein Momtaz et al, 2014 [11] observed oliguric in 77.5% of patients. Mathur NB, et al, 2007 [18] showed incidence of oliguric AKI to be 15%. Jayshree G et al, 1991 [23] showed incidence of oliguria to be 15%. In our study oliguric AKI was more prevalent because most common etiology in our study was sepsis and dehydration.

Table 8 shows mortality in our study was 36%. Hossein Momtaz et al [11] in their study revealed mortality to be 36.7% which is consistent with our study. Agras PL et al 2004 [19] found 24.4% mortality in their study. Kribben A et al, 1999 [8] described mortality closed to 50%. In Gharehbaghi et al 2007 [15] found a mortality of 20% in newborns affected with AKI. However Al idressy HM et al 1991 [12] reported mortality from renal failure was high at 77%. Table 9 shows the oliguric and non-oliguric AKI in neonates did not differ significantly with respect to weight, gestational age, onset of AKI. Mortality was found to be higher in those with oliguric AKI ($p=0.77$) Jayshree G, et al 1991 [23] showed high mortality in oliguric neonates.

Conclusion

The present study and observations clearly revealed that AKI is an increasingly recognised entity among critically ill neonates. In this study sepsis, birth asphyxia, RDS, PDA, PUV were common predisposing factors for AKI. Low birth weight and prematurity are important risk factors for the development of AKI. The most common causes of neonatal death in AKI in the present study was consistent with the most common causes of neonatal death including infections, prematurity and asphyxia. Higher mortality rate was associated with oliguric AKI states. AKI is independent risk factors for poor outcomes in critically ill neonates and this stresses the need to be screened for AKI in all sick newborns. In general prognosis of AKI in neonates is worse and therefore it is important to prevent AKI by rapid diagnosis of the patients with risk factors and effective treatment to reduce mortality. This is also felt that facilities for renal replacement therapy and Pediatric nephrology services should be available in all referral and tertiary neonatal centers.

Ethical approval: Ethics approval has been taken from IEC, SCB Medical College & SVPPGIP, and Cuttack.

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